

Case Report

Traumatic bilateral multiple ribs fractures in pregnancy

Swapnil Ravindra Bagdure¹⁼, Xuejian Wu^{1*}, Xinjiao Wang²⁼

¹Department of Orthopedics, The first affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, Henan, China

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, The first affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, Henan, China

⁼ Contributed equally as a first co-author

^{*}Corresponding author

Accepted: 16 November, 2020; Online: 16 November, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4276531>

Abstract: Traumatic bilateral multiple ribs fractures during pregnancy is a rare event. In this case author reports 41 years old multigravida women in 2nd trimester of pregnancy, presenting to hospital after a road traffic accident in a vulnerable condition. Physician must make sure the probable implications of the patient and the fetus. Accurate diagnosis is made using highly sensitive and specific computed tomography. Severely displaced ribs are fixed by open reduction internal fixation and remaining non-displaced ribs can be healed by conservative treatment. Proper analgesics are prescribed to manage pain pre and postoperatively. Physicians should cope with patient and family in making an effort to protect the child and continuing the pregnancy followed by regular fetal monitoring tests.

Keywords: Traumatic, Ribs fractures, Pregnancy, Preterm labor

Introduction

A non-obstetrical cause is being much more common compared to that of obstetrical causes of morbidity and mortality either in pregnant woman, fetus or both. In non-obstetrical causes trauma from penetrating injuries, blunt injuries from falling or road traffic accidents has become a leading factor ranging up to 6-7%. Complications including unfavorable outcomes such as injury or death of the mother, shock, internal hemorrhage, intrauterine fetal demise, direct injury to the fetus, spontaneous abortion, premature rupture of fetal membranes, preterm labor, cesarean section, placental abruption, and uterine rupture [1-3]. Based on some studies, trauma is the mortality cause in 46% of pregnant women and is the responsible cause in 5% of fetal demise

cases, while most trauma cases during pregnancy are minor traumas with good prognosis for mother and fetus [4-6]. Ribs fractures during pregnancy have previously been reported in the literature. The causes mentioned were associated with cough, stress and spontaneous fractures which have been treated either conservatively or surgically. Open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) has showed faster and better definitive outcomes. Traumatic bilateral multiple ribs fractures during pregnancy has not been mentioned earlier in the literature. Therefore we report this case providing the details on follow up and the outcomes of the patient and the fetus.

Case Presentation

On 1 July 2020 a 41 years old, multigravida pregnant women weighed 63 kg, presents with chest and back pain during 2nd trimester of her pregnancy was referred to our Orthopedic Department at First affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University. On 27th June 2020 she met a road traffic accident and was rushed at the local hospital, where she underwent computed tomography imaging and diagnosed with traumatic bilateral multiple ribs fractures and was under monitoring and conservative treatment, as condition was stabled she was transferred to our hospital. Upon physical examination tenderness and pain with chest deformity and subcutaneous hematoma was noted. Patient was anxious, confused, dehydrated, shallow tachypnea with tachycardia. Vital signs including temperature 36.3° C, blood pressure 105/90 mm Hg, pulse rate 80 beats/minute, respiratory rate 20 times/minute, oxygen saturation of 96%. Visual analogue scaling for pain was 6. Intravenous analgesia was prescribed to control pain. Laboratory examination including serum electrolytes, liver and gall bladder function tests, renal function tests, complete blood cells counts were all in normal limits. Inflammatory markers including ESR 100 mm/hour and CRP 32.2 mg/L levels were found to be higher.

Electrocardiogram of patient reported sinus tachycardia (106 beats/minute), premature atrial contraction and prolongation of QT interval (452 milliseconds). Computed tomography (CT) scans revealed bilateral multiple ribs fractured and moderate displacement on right side from 1-6 ribs and 1-9 ribs on left side with traceable amount of pleural effusion. 5th rib on the right side was moderately displaced at the angle of rib and lower ribs 6th, 7th and 9th on the left side were severely displaced between the neck and tubercle of the ribs (**Figure 1**). Ultrasound of lower leg

including bilateral femoral, popliteal, posterior and anterior tibial, fibular, intramuscular, dorsal foot veins embolus or clots were absent. Echocardiography showed ejection fraction of 60% and mild left ventricular diastolic function reduction while remaining other parameters were all within normal limits.

Discussing with patient and family about risks of surgery to the fetus, the informed consent was signed and on the next day 3rd July 2020 patient was prepared for surgery. Completing general anesthesia the patient was lied on the lateral side followed by a posterior thoracotomy. At the back the 10 cm long incision was made along the inferior-medial border of the scapula, through cauterizing and retracting soft tissues posterior thoracic muscles. Three moderate displaced ribs, the sixth, seventh and ninth were fixed using anatomical titanium reconstruction plates and cortical locking screws (3.5 mm thick and 8 mm width of product number FYSO4Med30, Beijing Fule Technology, Beijing, China). All the layers were carefully sutured and drainage tube was placed within the soft tissues to drain post-surgery accumulating fluids. The operation time was 2 hours 20 minutes and blood loss was around 100 ml. Postoperatively, cefuroxime and parecoxib was administered intravenously and continued for 5 days and later on only irecoxib was prescribed for the patient. On postoperative day 3 incision wound is examined and the drainage tube is removed followed by change dressing. Later the postoperative CT imaging was performed to recheck the correct fixation of the ribs (**Figure 2**).

Upon stabilized condition, the patient was transferred to obstetrics department for further evaluation of the fetus. Doppler ultrasound reported single fetus, fetal heart rate 139 beats/minute, bi-parietal diameter 43 mm, head circumference 161 mm, abdominal circumference 148 mm, femur length 29 mm, gestational age was calculated approximately to 19 weeks and 4 days.

Mostly prioritizing the mother's health, the doctor advised the patient and her family further to think for an abortion of the child, due to the risks of continuing the pregnancy keeping in mind about the medical, radiological and surgical threats to the fetus and increasing pressure of an enlarging fetus on the patient's body herself could result into unbearable pain or other postoperative complications including infection, bleeding or forming clots which could endangers both life.

Patient and her family confirmed to continue with the pregnancy and further raise the fetus. Proper medical counseling was provided on the basis of regular follow up every month till the delivery. On 22 October 2020, during 33rd weeks of pregnancy patient present to hospital complaining of bleeding and rupture of amniotic sac, epidural anesthesia was infused for analgesia before delivery. On the same day, the patient gave birth to baby girl through cesarean section.

Newborn girl weighed 2580 grams and with normal vital signs. On observation during 3rd day newborn girl looked pale and yellowish later on was diagnosed with jaundice. Following 2 weeks later she was completely recovered and was discharged from the hospital. During last follow up the physical and mental status of the patient was normal, the pain at her operated ribs were the only residual symptom persisted with a VAS score of 3 without affecting her daily routines.

Figure 1 Preoperative CT illustrating bilateral multiple ribs fracture

Figure 2 Postoperative CT illustrating ORIF of the displaced ribs

Discussion

Trauma in pregnancy can be a leading cause of injury and fatality in mother and fetus. The most common type of injury are motor vehicle accidents which can result into moderate to severe impact on health of the mother initially and on fetus eventually. The goal should be to prioritize the mother's health at first balancing her hemodynamics, stabilizing the vital signs and then taking care of other injuries including soft tissue bruises, fractures or any relating internal injuries. Keeping in mind that fetus could only do well if the mother is in good healthy state that includes the passageway, the passenger, the power, and the most important the psyche of the mother.

Physiological changes occur in pregnancy to nurture the developing fetus and prepare the mother for labor and delivery. Some of these changes influence normal biochemical values while others may mimic symptoms of medical disease. It is important to differentiate between normal physiological changes and disease pathology. There is controversy regarding the effect of pregnancy on maternal bone loss. Although pregnancy and lactation are associated with reversible bone loss, studies do not support an association between parity and osteoporosis in later life [7]. Bone turnover is low in the first trimester and increases in the third trimester when

fetal calcium needs are increased. The source of the calcium in the third trimester is previously stored skeletal calcium [8].

During pregnancy there is an increased risk of pulmonary embolisms due to stasis of blood in the veins and changes in physiology of blood coagulation [9]. At present patient's blood work was normal and the clinical signs were so specific for a rib fracture but were not accurate for the numbers of ribs fracture and degree of their displacement. The diagnostic tool for choosing computed tomography over chest radiography is its high sensitivity and specificity for ribs fractures [10-11]. In present author's opinion, the value of an additional postoperative CT was relatively higher to check the correct fixation of ribs prior to discharge of the patient.

Previous study described 35 cases of patients with a rib fracture due to coughing during the third trimester of pregnancy. The most of these patients had fractures of ribs VIII to XI, while in non-pregnant women, ribs VI and VII were fractured most of the time. The ribs fractures has a mechanic cause and described the (patho) mechanic changes of the rib cage during pregnancy in which the ribs are moved cranially and more horizontally due to the enlarging uterus. The lower ribs are pulled in a cranial direction by the intercostal, serratus anterior, and the latissimus dorsi muscles, while the external oblique and internal oblique muscles pull the rib cage in the contralateral (caudal) direction. This causes a certain tension on the lower ribs, and an unsuspected force, for example coughing or a minor trauma, can cause a fracture [12-15]. This remains the cause for this patient's postoperative residual pain at the operated site.

A learning point in this specific case, even during pregnancy to obtain an adequate diagnosis for complex degree of ribs fractures and displacement either ipsilaterally or bilaterally and can be well managed by both ways either conservatively or surgically by fixing the displaced ones using reconstruction plates and screws. Pregnancy is at threat but should be carefully monitored under expert's guidance. The treatment of a traumatic multiple ribs fractures is open reduction and closed fixation. In the current literature, there is agreement on what kind of treatment is the most effective. The patient further received epidural analgesia during labor, but there are no recommendations of appropriate analgesia during pregnancy.

Conclusion

Road traffic accidents leading to bilateral multiple displaced ribs fractures are rare incidents during pregnancy and can have a huge uneventful moderate to severe impact on mother's and fetus health. They may sometimes result into undesirable outcomes either to one or both of them. It's completely a physician responsibility to inform the patient and their family of various possibilities that may result into. Hemodynamics of the mother should be stabilized quickly and fractures should be managed using proper diagnostic tools such as computed tomography and opting surgical fixation. Upon proper medical counseling and monitoring the fetus health, the pregnancy can be continued.

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Dr. Swapnil Ravindra Bagdure
MBBS at Zhengzhou University.
Currently 3rd year Master’s student in Orthopedics at Zhengzhou University.

Dr. Xinjiao Wang
Bachelor’s at Huanghe Science and Technology University.
Fellowship in Obstetrics and Gynecology at
First affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University.

Acknowledgments

The completion of this undertaking could not have been possible without the participation and constant assistance of Dr. Xinjiao Wang. Thanks to Dr. Xuejian Wu for your interest in this case and supporting me throughout the study. Grateful to my mother Dr. Bharati Bagdure for her constant motivation. Finally need to thank all the doctors in our family including my grandfather, uncle's, aunt's and other relatives.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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The graphic features a stylized green globe with a plant growing out of it, set against a background of radiating lines.

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